

The Effect of Marketing Mix on Customer Satisfaction in Belawan Branch of PT Pelabuhan Indonesia 1 (Persero) Medan

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ABSTRACT

It is important to maintain an ongoing good relationship with service users so that there will be satisfaction by service users who have established good relations with PT Pelindo Medan 1, especially the port of Belawan. The research objective is to determine the effect of marketing mix includes (product, price, promotion, distribution, people, process, and physical evidence) partially on customer satisfaction of product at the port of Belawan, knowing the effect of marketing mix includes (product, price, promotion, distribution, people, process, and physical evidence) simultaneously on product customer satisfaction at the Belawan port, knowing the most dominant factor influencing from the marketing mix of product, price, promotion, distribution, people, process, and physical evidence on the customer satisfaction of products at the Belawan port. The study uses quantitative research methods with a sample of 94 respondents. The results of the study showed. Simultaneously the marketing mix (product, price, place, promotion, people, process and physical evidence) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the Belawan port and partially the promotion, price, person and process variables affect customer satisfaction at Belawan Port. However, product, place and physical evidence do not affect consumer satisfaction at Belawan Harbor.

Keywords: Marketing Mix, Customer Satisfaction, Product, Price

INTRODUCTION

PT Pelabuhan Indonesia (Persero) (PELINDO) used to be in the Dutch

colonial era, a company that has the name "Haven Bedrijf". Belawan Port is part of the port owned by PT Pelabuhan Indonesia 1 (PELINDO 1). Belawan Port is one of the nationalized assets. After the independence of the Republic of Indonesia, in the period of 1951 the status of "Heaven Bedrijf" for the management of ports in Indonesia was changed to Port Bureau, under the Head of the Port. Since 1956-1961 the name of the Port Bureau was changed to the State Port Company led by the Director of the State Port Company.

In this study the increase in customer satisfaction at PT Pelabuhan Indonesia 1 (PELINDO 1) Belawan Branch is related to marketing mix (7P: product, price, promotion, place, people, physical evidence, process), because the Belawan port branch there are several problems related to The marketing mix is indicated to be the cause of decreased customer satisfaction. This is due to some products experiencing a decline in sales at the Belawan port branch. As a company that has a monopoly of ports around the North Sumatra region, companies should be able to provide the best service, but sometimes the facts in the field are different from the reality, especially the Belawan Port Branch.

Based on the data and observations of researchers related to the trash can is still a problem in Belawan Harbor today. The waters of Belawan Harbor are still full of garbage scattered along the Belawan Harbor pond because the community around the

port still uses the sea as trash cans (<http://www.medanbisnisdaily.com>, 2019). In addition to being related to people, shipping business operators complain that the siltation of port lanes and ponds due to sedimentation is not immediately addressed by the port manager or the relevant authority. This is because the silting up causes the level of ship occupancy to not be optimal. In addition, the data shows that public docks and special docks based on the type of trade have decreased customer satisfaction.

Apart from that, related to the tariff (price in the marketing mix), Belawan Port cannot make various efforts to raise or reduce prices that are not in accordance with the Ministerial Regulation, namely PM 2002-2017. Belawan Harbor. Therefore, the authors are interested in conducting research relating to the perceptions of users of Pelindo services related to the marketing mix, including price and physical evidence. In addition, with regard to service processes, some processes tend to have slow service caused by several conditions and situations. Associated with the promotion of some service users sometimes do not get information about the promotion due to promotion of inequality by the company.

Based on research partially the marketing mix consisting of: product, price, promotion, distribution, people, physical evidence and the process of significant influence and the relationship is positive or in the direction of changes to customer satisfaction at the company (Alma, 2008). Simultaneous product, price, promotion, distribution, people, physical evidence and process have a significant effect and the relationship is positive or in the same direction of change to customer satisfaction in the company and the seven dimensions of the marketing mix variable that most influences customer satisfaction in a row are: price, physical evidence, process, distribution, people and promotions. The results showed that the marketing mix consisting of products, prices, promotions and distribution channels simultaneously

had an influence on customer satisfaction at the company.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Marketing Mix

In marketing in the service sector it is said to be an act or act that moves from one party to another and is marketing intangible services. Service marketing usually uses a marketing tool that is known as "4P" and to date has experienced a development to become "7P" which is used as a marketing tool in the service sector (Lupiyoadi, 2013).

2.2 Product

Kotler (2012) provides a product definition that is as everything that is usually offered to the market to provide satisfaction to the wants or needs of consumers. Products are usually divided into sub sections namely goods and services produced to the target market to meet the needs and desires.

In addition, Kotler and Armstrong (2012) state that the product in question is related to quality products, which are offered to the market at affordable prices. It was also revealed that the product brand was important because several segments in the market used the brand as a reference in determining the product to be purchased.

2.3 Price

Kotler (2012) says that the price of an amount of money is as an exchange rate to get the benefits of using a product or service. Prices become part of the marketing mix that is flexible where prices can be stable over a certain period of time but prices can also increase or decrease. Kotler and Armstrong (2012) add price as an important element inherent in the product or service. Price can be the main key for customers in buying goods or services.

2.4 Place

Kotler (2012) says place is an action taken by a company to make its products easily available and available to

consumers/customers. In addition, Kotler and Armstrong (2012) state that a place is related to product access and product distribution. Location becomes an important role in marketing because it is related to after-sales satisfaction and before-sales customer satisfaction.

2.5 Promotion

Promotion according to Kotler (2012) is all activities carried out by companies to communicate and promote their products to the target market. Then Kotler and Armstrong (2012) stated that promotion is a tool in marketing a product. This promotion also then eroded the company's finances in order to introduce its products to the market. Prominent forms of advertising in print and electronic media, brochures, billboards, sponsorships and online media.

2.6 People

According to Kotler (2012), people are the process of selecting, training and motivating employees, which later can be used as a differentiation of the company in meeting customer satisfaction. Then Kotler and Armstrong (2012) state that people are commitment, incentives, appearance, behavior, and habits. Whatever is attached to the customers or company employees.

2.7 Physical Evidence

Physical evidence according to Kotler (2012) is evidence that is owned by the service provider addressed to the customer as a proposed value added customer. Physical proof is a tangible form offered to customers or prospective customers.

Then Kotler and Armstrong (2012) state that physical evidence is an environment, color, layout, and additional facilities. This is related to the appearance of a product/service offered related to packaging, which is presented to attract customers. This process is one of the core elements in 9 core elements of marketing, but seeing an important correlation, this

element is pulled into one part of the marketing mix. Some process indicators needed are procedures, policies, mechanization, direction of activities, and so on.

2.8 Process

Process is all the actual procedures, mechanisms and activity flow through which services is delivered which is the presentation system for service operations. Then Kotler and Armstrong (2012) stated that the process is one of the core elements in the 9 core elements of marketing, but seeing an important correlation then this element is pulled into one part in the marketing mix. Some process indicators needed are procedures, policies, mechanization, direction of activities, and so on.

2.9 Customer Satisfaction

According to Tjiptono (2012) customer satisfaction is someone's happy or disappointed feelings that arise after comparing perceptions of the performance of a product with its expectations. In addition, Daryanto and Setyobudi (2014) stated that customer satisfaction is an emotional assessment of the customer after the customer uses a product where the expectations and needs of customers who use it are met.

RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Types of Research

This research uses correlation research. Which divides the data into two parts namely 1) primary data and 2) secondary data. The customer perception of PT Pelabuhan Indonesia 1 (PELINDO 1) Belawan Branch regarding the marketing mix is the primary data. To find out these perceptions questionnaires were distributed as research instruments. Meanwhile, company data and information obtained from documents owned by the company are secondary data.

3.2 Location and Time of Research

The study is located at PT Pelabuhan Indonesia 1 (PELINDO 1) Belawan North Sumatra Branch of service users with an estimated time of research that is from June 2019 to August 2019.

3.3 Population and Samples

Population is an area where researchers will form ideas that include quality objects or subjects and have certain characteristics that have been set for later study by researchers and eventually conclusions will be drawn (Sugiyono, 2014). The population in this study is the number of service users of PT Pelabuhan

Indonesia 1 (PELINDO 1) Belawan Port Branch as many as 305 service users.

The minimum number of samples is: $8 \times 10 = 80$ respondents. Using 94 respondents in this study was considered adequate.

3.4 Data Analysis Method

Data analysis method is a method or method used to conduct research data processing in order to obtain an instrument and conclusions. Multiple linear analysis as a method of data analysis in this study. Hypothesis testing uses simultaneous, partial test, and the coefficient of determination.

RESULT

Simultaneous Test (F Test)

Table 1. ANOVA Research Model

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	739.832	7	105.690	122.323	.000 ^b
	Residual	74.306	86	.864		
	Total	814.138	93			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Physical Evidence, Product, Price, Process, Place, Promotion, People

Source: Research Results

Table 1 provides information that together the independent variables of product, place, price, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence can significantly influence customer satisfaction. This decision was obtained based on an F-calculated value greater than the F-table, or through a F-test significance value smaller than 0.05 (Sig F = 0.000). Thus the independent variables of product, place, price, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence are true as predictors for the satisfaction of Belawan port service users.

Partial Test (t Test)

Table 2. Regression Coefficient of the Research Model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.251	.805		.312	.756
	Product	.027	.047	.035	.580	.563
	Place	.038	.050	.032	.773	.442
	Promotion	-.266	.082	-.193	-3.252	.002
	Price	.142	.057	.130	2.478	.015
	People	.115	.057	.122	2.028	.046
	Process	.800	.037	.869	21.618	.000
	Physical Evidence	.056	.038	.054	1.472	.145

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source: Research Results

The regression equation above indicates that the customer satisfaction variable is influenced by the promotion variables (0.002), price (0.015), people (0.046) and process (0.000) because the significance value is smaller than 0.05. But

the promotion variable has a negative effect. Meanwhile the variables that have no significant effect are: product (0.563), place (0.042) and physical evidence (0.145) because the significance value is greater than 0.05. In this model, customer

satisfaction (service users) will increase/decrease if:

1. B (0.251) or constant is also called intercept (a). This means that if the port of Belawan does not implement the marketing mix strategy namely product, price, place, promotion, process, people or physical evidence or value 0, then customer satisfaction is 0.251. Negative constants are not a concern in this study as long as the regression model that you test meets the assumptions (normality test, autocorrelation test, heteroskedasticity test and multicolinearity test). In addition, as long as the slope value is not zero then there is no need to care about this negative constant. Negative constants generally occur if there is a sufficiently large range between X (independent variable) and Y.

2. The product regression coefficient value is 0.027, meaning that if the value of the product changes one unit, then customer satisfaction (service users) will change by 0.027. The positive sign in the regression indicates a direct relationship between the product and customer satisfaction. This means that if the product increases, customer satisfaction will also increase. But seeing the significance value of the product variable does not significantly affect customer satisfaction at the Belawan branch port because the significance value > 0.05 . The positive effect shows that the better the presentation of products or services offered by the Belawan Branch Port of PT Pelindo 1, the greater the level of customer satisfaction (service users) in buying and consuming products. The most respondents are container users, loading and unloading and shipping together.

3. The value of the place regression coefficient is 0.038, meaning that if the place value changes to one unit, then customer satisfaction will change by 0.038. The positive sign on the regression indicates a direct relationship between place and customer satisfaction. This means that if the place increases, customer satisfaction will also increase. But seeing the significant value of the place variable does not

significantly affect customer satisfaction at the Belawan branch port because the significance value > 0.05 . On the variable where the access of service users in reaching Belawan Harbor is still felt by the service user difficulties. To reach the position of Belawan Harbor, service users are often required to use a car or private vehicle.

4. The promotion regression coefficient value is -0.266, meaning that if the promotion value changes one unit, then customer satisfaction will change by -0.266. The negative value sign in the regression indicates the opposite relationship between promotion and customer satisfaction. This means that if the promotion increases customer satisfaction will decrease. Seeing the significance value, the promotion variable has a significant effect on customer satisfaction due to the significance value < 0.05 . This is in accordance partially the promotion marketing mix has a significant effect and the relationship is positive or in the direction of the changes to customer satisfaction at the company. However, at the Port of Belawan Branch of PT Pelindo 1 if efforts are made to increase promotion as one of the company's marketing mix strategies, customer satisfaction (service users) will decrease. So the promotion does not need to be increased to increase customer satisfaction because it gives a significant influence in the opposite direction (negative).

5. The value of the price regression coefficient is 0.142, meaning that if the price value changes to one unit, then customer satisfaction will change by 0.142. The positive value sign in the regression indicates a direct relationship between price and customer satisfaction. This means that if the price, then customer satisfaction will also increase. Seeing the significance value then the variable price has a significant effect on customer satisfaction due to the significance value < 0.05 . This is in accordance partially the marketing mix has a significant effect on the price and the

relationship is positive or in the direction of the changes to customer satisfaction at the company. This means that if the Port of Belawan Branch of PT Pelindo 1 carries out several price change strategies, it will provide satisfaction to the customers (service users).

6.The value of the regression coefficient of people is 0.115, meaning that if the value of people changes to one unit, then customer satisfaction will change by 0.115. The positive sign in the regression indicates a direct relationship between people and customer satisfaction. This means that if people increase, customer satisfaction will also increase. Seeing the significance value, the variable of people has a significant influence on customer satisfaction due to the significance value < 0.05. This is in accordance with research conducted partially the marketing mix which consists of significant influential people and the relationship is positive or unidirectional to changes in customer satisfaction at the company. This means that if the Belawan Branch Port of PT. Pelindo 1 improves soft and employee skills by attending various training provided and facilitated by companies that directly provide services to customers, so customer satisfaction will increase.

7.The process regression coefficient value is 0.800, meaning that if the process value changes to one unit, then customer satisfaction will change by 0.800. Seeing the significance value, the process variables significantly influence customer satisfaction. This is in accordance with research conducted partially the marketing mix which consists of a process of significant influence and the relationship is positive or in the direction of changes to customer satisfaction at the company. This means that if the Port of Belawan Branch of PT Pelindo 1 improves the stages or process of services that can accelerate and facilitate service users in using services, customer satisfaction (service users) will increase.

8.The regression coefficient value of physical evidence is 0.056, meaning that if the value of physical evidence changes one unit, then customer satisfaction will change by 0.056. The positive sign in the regression indicates a direct relationship between physical evidence and the purchase decision. This means that if physical evidence increases, customer satisfaction will also increase. Seeing the significance value, the physical evidence variable does not significantly affect customer satisfaction due to the significance value > 0.05.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Tabel 3. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.953 ^a	.909	.901	.92953	2.003
a. Predictors: (Constant), Physical Evidence, Product, Price, Process, Placet, Promotion, People					
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction					

Table 3 provides information about the predictive ability of the research model in the Research model. The adjusted R-square value in the Research Model indicates that the independent variables of product, place, price, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence are able to explain 90.9% of data variance on the dependent variable of customer satisfaction (Y). The rest, as much as 9.1% of the data variance on customer satisfaction is explained by other variables not examined in this model.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

The conclusions in this study are:

1.Marketing mix (product mix, product, price, place, promotion, people, process and physical evidence) together have a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction (Y) at the Belawan Branch Port of PT. Indonesian Port 1 (PELINDO 1) Medan.

2.Partially, promotion, price, people and process variables have a significant

influence on customer satisfaction at the Belawan Branch Port of PT. Indonesian Port 1 (PELINDO 1) Medan. However, product, place and physical evidence do not have a significant influence on customer satisfaction at the Belawan Branch Port of PT. Indonesian Port 1 (PELINDO 1) Medan.

SUGGESTION

Researcher's suggestions for the company are as follows:

1.Regarding the product (service), the satisfaction of users by the belawan port will be influenced by the services provided by the belawan port. The focus of all businesses remains on providing services to provide satisfaction to service users and to meet the needs and desires of service users.

2.Connecting with people, training to improve the ability in terms of soft skills and hard skills to employees on an ongoing and periodic basis is needed, for example, every 3 months. Then performance appraisals are performed on employees so there is no decline in performance in carrying out services to customers.

3.Related to the promotion, enhancement or improvement of promotional content on the website is more of a concern. As to make the website user friendly and provide information that is easily understood by service users. Appearance of the website in accordance with the needs and desires of service users will make promotions carried out by the port of Belawan be on target.

4.Regarding the place, the cleanliness of Belawan harbor is still a matter that needs to be considered by the company. With all the convenience of cleaning accommodation

and the needs of service users should be the company's attention.

5.Due to prices, the port cannot change prices. Because prices are clearly written in the regulations.

6.Regarding the process, Belawan Port has carried out the process procedures in accordance with the port SOP, but the service is still not fast enough. So the speed of service time is the main suggestion in this study.

7.In connection with physical evidence for the availability of waiting rooms, it is better for the cleanliness and comfort of service users to be a concern for Belawan Harbor.

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